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uint16_t getIntMassFromResponseFrame(char *s, uint16_t *decimal_mass){
    uint16_t mass_in_int =0;
    char number[9];
    char decimal[9];
    int point=0;
    int j=0;
    for(int i=6;i<15;i++){
        if(s[i] != ' '){
            if (s[i] != '.')
                number[j++]=s[i];
            else{
                point = i;
                break;
            }
        }
    }

    j=0;
    for(int i=point+1;i<15;i++){
        if(s[i] != ' ')
            decimal[j++]=s[i];
        else
            break;
    }
    mass_in_int = atoi(number);
    *decimal_mass = atoi(decimal);
    return mass_in_int;
}

uint8_t MassDosageFunction(uint16_t *measured_mass){
    int16_t delta2=0;
    int16_t delta1=0;
    if(HAL_GPIO_ReadPin(STOP_btn_GPIO_Port,STOP_btn_Pin) == GPIO_PIN_RESET){
        StepperStop(&M1,ENDSTOP_NOT_PRESSED);
        return 1;
    }

    if(*measured_mass<mp70percent){
        //TODO change speed to fast
        StepperSetSteppsPerSecond(&M1,fast_speed);
    }
    if(*measured_mass>=mp70percent && *measured_mass<mp90percent){
        //TODO change speed to medium
        StepperSetSteppsPerSecond(&M1,medium_speed);
        predkosc[0] = 'm';
    }

    if(*measured_mass>=mp90percent && *measured_mass<mp97percent){
        //TODO change speed to slow
        StepperSetSteppsPerSecond(&M1,slow_speed);
        predkosc[0] = 's';
    }

    if(*measured_mass>=mp97percent){
        //TODO switch OFF the motor and go to while loop
        StepperStop(&M1,ENDSTOP_NOT_PRESSED);
        predkosc[0] = '0';
        while(1){

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GPIO_PIN_RESET){
    if(HAL_GPIO_ReadPin(STOP_btn_GPIO_Port,STOP_btn_Pin) ==
        StepperStop(&M1,ENDSTOP_NOT_PRESSED);
        return 1;
    }
    //TODO wait until motor is stopped to get stabilized mass
measure and convert frame to two numbers - finite number and decimal
    while(M1.status == MOTOR_ON);

    if(M1.status == MOTOR_OFF){
        HAL_UART_Transmit(&huart3,podaj_wynik_teraz,5,10);
        HAL_UART_Receive(&huart3,data_buffer,21,500);
        *measured_mass = getIntMassFromResponseFrame((char
*)(data_buffer),&decimal_mass_value);
    }

    delta1= mp-(*measured_mass);
    if(delta1>0){
        if(delta1>1){
            //TODO move motor with 10 steps on minimal speed
            HAL_Delay(300);
            StepperMoveWithStepsNumber(&M1,100);
            HAL_Delay(300);
        }
        else{
            delta2 = 10-decimal_mass_value;

            if(delta2>=6){
                //TODO move motor with 5 steps on minimal
speed
                HAL_Delay(500);
                StepperMoveWithStepsNumber(&M1,50);
                HAL_Delay(500);
            }
            else{
                //TODO shutdown the MOTOR and signal PLC
that dosing material is completed EXIT THE LOOP
                StepperStop(&M1,ENDSTOP_NOT_PRESSED);

                HAL_GPIO_WritePin(DosageDoneSignal_GPIO_Port,DosageDoneSignal_Pin,GPIO_PIN_S
ET);

                return 1;
            }
        }
    }
    else if(delta1==0){
        StepperStop(&M1,ENDSTOP_NOT_PRESSED);

        HAL_GPIO_WritePin(DosageDoneSignal_GPIO_Port,DosageDoneSignal_Pin,GPIO_PIN_S
ET);

        return 1;
    }
    else{
        if(delta1<-1){
            //TODO call operator to get rid off the excessive
mass

            HAL_GPIO_WritePin(LD2_GPIO_Port,LD2_Pin,GPIO_PIN_SET);

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        return 1;
    }
    else{
        delta2 = -decimal_mass_value;
        //TODO shutdown the MOTOR and signal PLC that
dosing material is completed EXIT THE LOOP
        StepperStop(&M1,ENDSTOP_NOT_PRESSED);

        HAL_GPIO_WritePin(DosageDoneSignal_GPIO_Port,DosageDoneSignal_Pin,GPIO_PIN_S
ET);
        return 1;
    }
}
}
return 0;
}
```